

PRODUCTION OF OIL-WELL CEMENT USING LOCAL RAW MATERIALS

*¹A.U. Bagudo, ²M.N. Almustapha, ³M.L. Muhammed, ⁴A.B. Mohammad ⁵Ahmad, B.R and ⁶Hamisu A.R, Ahmad Rufai

¹²³⁴⁶Department of Energy and Applied Chemistry, UsmanuDanfodiyo University, Sokoto, Nigeria

⁵Department of Chemistry, Nigerian Army University Biu , Borno State, Nigeria

(Corresponding Author:Email:bagudoa52@gmail.com; +2347030234636)

(Co-authors Email: ² nurudeen.almustapha@udusok.edu.ng, ³ misbahu.ladan@udusok.edu.ng,

⁴ muhammad.aminu@udusok.edu.ng ⁵ ahmadbilyaminu@naub.edu.ng and ⁶ rufee14@gmail.com)

ABSTRACT

Oil wells are typically encased and cemented with a specialised cement to stabilise the wellbore and isolate problematic zones, thereby maximising production. This research aims to develop a Novel cement using Type II clinker and locally abundant laterite. The laterite was oven-dried at 200°C for 15minutes and analysed with X-ray Fluorescence prior to being milled and calcined with the clinker. The pure laterite exhibited an iron content of 42.552% (Fe₂O₃ 3 wt%), indicating its potential as a corrective additive on Type II clinker. The newly formulated oil-well cement (POWCH5), demonstrated the following composition: 54.4727 wt% tricalcium silicate (C₃S), 17.2568 wt% dicalcium silicate (C₂S), 5.8245 wt% tricalcium aluminate (C₃A), 15.7196 wt% tetracalcium aluminoferrite (C₄AF), and a specific surface area of 331 m²/kg. These characteristics, particularly the low C₃A and high C₄AF content, are advantageous for oil-well cement, leading to extended setting times. The POWCH5 cement aligns with the Class G (MRS) Oil-well cement standards set forth by the American Petroleum Institute (API) Specification 10A and corroborated by literature.

Keywords: BUAC: BUA Cement; BUACL: BUA Cement's Clinker; BOWC: By weight of cement (POWCH5: New Developed Oil-Well Cement. MSR: Moderate sulphate resistant.

1. INTRODUCTION

Cement is a crystalline compound of calcium silicates and other calcium compounds having hydraulic properties (Ede *et al.*, 2021). Cement could also be defined as material/substance which exhibits properties capable of binding material fragments into one-whole when mixed with water (Paruthi *et al.*, 2023).

Specifications in the Cement industry are based partly on chemical composition and partially on physical properties such as specific surface area, and partly on performance tests, such as setting time or compressive strength developed under standard conditions. Thus different types of cement are manufactured for different requirements (Chen *et al.*, 2024).

Chemical composition of cement includes the oxides and mineralogical compositions. The chemical oxides include major oxides as CaO, SiO₂, Al₂O₃ and Fe₂O₃, minor oxides as SO₃,

MgO and alkali oxides (K_2O and Na_2O) and sometimes the inclusion of P_2O_3 , Mn_2O_3 , Cl and so forth while the mineralogical composition include C_3S , C_2S , C_3A and C_4AF (Haha *et al.*, 2023.).

Cement can be classified into calcium silicates and calcium aluminates depending on its composition; calcium silicate cement is further classified into Portland cement and Slag cement; while calcium aluminates are classified into high alumina cement and pozzolana cement. Other types of cement are known as special cements; such as oil well cement (Farooq *et al.*, 202.). Oil well cement is a special type of cement that is characterised by low tricalcium aluminate (C_3A) and high ferrite phase (C_4AF) Fan *et al.* (2022).

The American Petroleum Institute (API) specification (10a) designates eight types of Oil well cement, Classes A through H. Each class is specified for use in a certain range of well depth, temperature and pressure (Bageri *et al.*, 2021).

API 10a also designates three grades of Oil-well cement to address sulfate environments viz Grade O: Ordinary, Grade MSR: Moderate sulfate resistance and Grade HSR: High sulfate resistance (Suleimanov *et al.*, 2023).

Davoodi *et al.* (2024) synthesized an amphoteric composite polymer (PAADM) as a high temperature-resistant cement retarder by in situ intercalated polymerization method with 2-crylamido-2- methylpropanesulfonic acid (AMPS), acrylic acid (AA) and two diallyl dimethyl ammonium chloride (DMDAAC) as monomers, and modified montmorillonite as an active polymerization filler. Performance evaluation evidenced that the cement slurry containing PAADM has good retarding property in the range of $120^{\circ}C$ – $200^{\circ}C$, and demonstrated the rapid development of compressive strength under high temperature and low temperature conditions, this property could guarantee that the retarder PAADM could be applied to the deep of oil wells and long interval oil wells. On XRD analysis of Class G MSR oil well cement used in the research revealed chemical compositions as CaO, SiO_2 , Fe_2O_3 , Al_2O_3 , SO_3 , MgO, K_2O , Na_2O and Others as 59.80 22.40 7.60, 2.70 2.40 2.60 0.60 0.20 0.70 wt% respectively while the phases as C_3S , C_2S , C_3A , C_4AF , $CaSO_4$ and others as 49.30, 24.70, 6.80, 11.0, 4.10 and 3.80 wt% respectively.

Oil well cement was developed from Portland cement type CP III 40 RS (Blast furnace slag Portland cement – sulfate resistant) a Brazil brand from CIMEC Company. The methodology used for the obtainment of the new cement consisted of the sieving of the CPIII through ABNT 200 and ABNT 325 sieves. The Characterisation of the new cement developed revealed chemical compositions as CaO, SiO_2 , Al_2O_3 , SO_3 , MgO, Fe_2O_3 , K_2O , TiO_3 as 46.6, 23.5, 12.9, 7.6, 6.6, 1.1, 0.6 and 0.6 percentage respectively while quantitative phases as C_3S , C_2S , C_3A , C_4AF and $C_4AF+2.C_3A$ as 57.13, 12.20, 3.92, 26.74 and 34.59 Wt% respectively. The physical analysis of the new developed cement revealed initial setting time and final setting time as 561 (mins) and 646 mins respectively while Compressive Strength for 1 day and 14 days as 1.55 Mpa and 13.05 Mpa respectively (Bahrami *et al.*, 2024)

Ahmed *et al.*, 2020 incorporated tire waste material as an additives into Saudi class G oil well cement slurry to improve cement matrix durability under high Temperature and Pressure conditions of 292 F and 3000psi. The results revealed incorporating 0.3% by weight of cement (BWOC) of the tire waste material-plastic viscosity is decreased by 53.1%, yield point is

increased by 142.4%, young modulus is decreased by 10.8% and poison ratio increased by 14.3% compared to the base cement.

Laterite refer to the more strongly cemented or replaced materials that contain a minimum of 50% of the cementing material-iron and aluminium oxides (Dissanayake *et al.*, 2021).

Laterite has been used for centuries as a construction material in building low income houses (local) but its most effective use has been in the area of road construction. It has found useful application as a sub-base material in the construction of highway pavement (Vincent *et al.*, 2020).

Bandara and Kawamoto (2022) proposed different strategies to develop a low cost adsorbent using laterite, a natural ore easily available. On XRF analysis of two laterite ores i.e Upper and Lower ores revealed compositions as Fe_2O_3 as 26.2%, MgO as 1.19%, Al_2O_3 as 56.55%, P_2O_5 as 0.25%, TiO_2 as 4.22%, SiO_2 as 9.96%, Mn_3O_4 as 0.2%, CaO as 0.8%, Na_2O as 0.16%, V_2O_5 as 0.12%, Cr_2O_3 as 0.08% and LOI as 22.94% and Fe_2O_3 as 31.97%, MgO as 0.92%, Al_2O_3 as 33.29%, P_2O_5 as 0.23%, TiO_2 as 4.05%, SiO_2 as 27.54%, Mn_3O_4 as 0.23%, CaO as 0.6%, Na_2O as 0.12%, V_2O_5 as 0.13%, Cr_2O_3 as 0.11% and LOI as 13.52% respectively.

A comparative analysis of the chemical and mineralogical compositions of different cement types reveals significant differences that influence performance and suitability for specific applications. Nuhu *et al.* (2020), in their study on Sokoto cement (BUA), reported a relatively low iron (Fe_2O_3) content and a correspondingly high tricalcium aluminate (C_3A) content, which resulted in a reduced amount of tetracalcium aluminoferrite (C_4AF). This composition contrasts with that of oil-well cement, as analyzed by Ahmed *et al.* (2021), which exhibited higher iron content, leading to greater formation of C_4AF and lower levels of C_3A .

These variations are of critical importance, as the C_3A and C_4AF contents influence cement behavior in aggressive environments. While high C_3A levels may accelerate early strength development, they also increase susceptibility to sulphate attack, which can be problematic in oil-well applications. In contrast, higher C_4AF levels are generally associated with improved sulphate resistance and reduced heat of hydration, making such cements more suitable for deep-well and high-temperature conditions.

This comparison highlights the importance of tailoring cement composition to its intended use, as different applications demand varying performance characteristics, which are directly influenced by the clinker phase composition and raw material selection. Thus correcting materials enrich in iron should be sourced and this brought about the use of an iron-rich laterite in this research.

Oil well cements (OWC) are used in oil and gas industries. The primary role is to seal space between the walls of a borehole and secure the steel casing that lines the well, thus require tighter specification than construction cement. In spite of its tremendous importance particularly in the oil industry, OWC is expensive and currently imported by both local and multinationals companies operating in Nigeria.

To the best of my knowledge, no study was carried on the production of Oil-well cement by modification of type II cement's clinker using laterite which is readily available in Nigeria.

This research work is aimed at modifying Type II (Bua) cement's clinker using locally available laterite for the production of Class G (MSR) Oil- Well Cement (OWC) for the oil and gas industry

2.0 Materials and Methodology

2.1 Sample Collection

Type II (BUAC) cement, type II (BUACL) cement's clinker, Gypsum and Laterites were all obtained from Bua Cement company plc. , Sokoto state. The analysis was conducted in the laboratory of Bua Cement Company plc. Sokoto State formally known as Cement Company of Northern Nigeria (CCNN), in accordance with the procedure stated in the quality control manual of the Company.

2.2 Preparation of Reagents

2.2.1 Barium Chloride (10 % w/w)

Exactly 50g of BaCl₂ was dissolved in 500 cm³ of distilled water.

2.2.2 Methyl Red Indicator Solution (0.1 % w/w).

Exactly 0.1g of methyl red was dissolved in 100cm³ of ethanol.

2.2.3 Sodium Hydroxide Solution (0.25M)

About 5g of Sodium hydroxide was dissolved in approximately 500 cm³ of distilled water in 1000ml volumetric flask, made up to the marked and stored in polyethylene flask.

2.2.4 Ammonium Chloride Solution (0.2M)

About 21.4g of NH₄Cl was weighed and dissolved in 2000 cm³ of distilled water.

2.3 Drying Zone (Evaporation of free water)/Determination of Moisture Contents of Laterites.

3.2.3 Drying Zone (Evaporation of free water)/ Determination of Moisture Content.

Exactly 100g of laterite samples (LAT A and LAT B) was placed separately in a pre-weighed dried aluminium dishes and pre-heated in an oven at 200°C for 15 minutes, after which the dishes was removed and allowed to cool and reweighed (C.C.N.N. , 2000).The percentage moisture content was calculated as:

$$\% \text{McL} = \frac{WmL - WdL}{WdL} \times 100$$

Moisture Content of laterite = McL
WmL = Weight of moist laterite,
WdL = weight of dry laterite

About 10g of the pre-heated Lat A and Lab B, BUAC, BUACL and the new cement developed was crushed using mortar and pestle and milled for 3 minutes using vibratory cup milling machine. From milled and crushed samples, 3g was weighed and ignited in a muffle furnace at 1000°C and taken for LOI, Glass beads formations and XRF analysis in section 2.5.3, 2.5.4 and 2.5.5 respectively.

2.4 Production of Oil well cement

2.4.1 Prepared Oil well cement at zero percent Laterite (POWCC)

About 4800g of crushed clinker and 200g of crushed gypsum representing 96% and 4% by weight of the cement (bwoc) respectively was crushed using crusher and grinded together (no laterite was added) using laboratory milling machine for about 45 minutes and allowed to discharge for 15 minutes which served as control and labelled POWCC.

2.4.2 Prepared Oil-well cement by milling of Clinker and laterite followed by calcination.

About 1365g of crushed clinker and 75g of laterite representing 91% and 5% laterite by weight of the cement (bwoc) respectively was grinded using laboratory milling machine for 45 minutes and allowed to discharge for 15 minutes. The product (grinded clinker and Laterite) in ceramic crucible (100mls) was placed in a furnace batch wise and heated at 1000°C for 5 minutes.

After ignition, the crucibles was removed and cooled in a desiccator. About 60g of crushed gypsum (representing 4% bwoc) was grinded using vibrating cup milling machine for 5 minutes. The grinded gypsum was mixed with the product (calcined clinker and laterite) and crushed together using pestle and mortar batch wise. The Oil-well cement produced was labeled POWCH5 sieved with 200 micro sieves and stored in a plastic container (Hasnain Haider *et al.*, 2024).

2.5 Determination of chemical parameters

These include; determination of SO₃ in gypsum, determination of insoluble residue in gypsum, lost of ignition of the samples, formation of beads by Claisse machine and X-ray fluorescence.

2.5.1 Determination of SO₃ in gypsum

Exactly 1.0g of crushed and milled gypsum was placed in a beaker and 10cm³ of warm distilled water was added followed by 5cm³ of concentrated hydrochloric acid. The mixture was stirred thoroughly and heated on hot plate to boiling. The solution was filtered using a blue ribbon filter paper into a 250cm³ beaker. The filtrate was boiled and 20cm³ of 10 % BaCl₂ was added.

The solution was allowed to stand for 2 hours. The cloudy solution was filtered using a blue ribbon filter paper to collect the residue. The filter paper containing the residue was placed in a pre-weighed ceramic crucible and ignited in the furnace for 30 minutes at 1000°C. After the ignition the sample and the crucible was allowed to cool at a constant weight in a desiccator (CCNN, 2000).

The percentage of sulphur trioxide was calculated using

$$\%SO_3 = 0.343 \frac{w_2 - w_1}{w} \times 100$$

Where $w_2 = \text{final weight of the sample}$, $w_1 = \text{initial weight of the sample}$ and $w = \text{weight of the sample}$

2.5.2 Determination of insoluble residue in gypsum

Exactly 1.0g of crushed and milled gypsum was placed into 250cm³ beaker and 5cm³ of concentrated hydrochloric acid was added followed by 100cm³ of warm distilled water.

The mixture was stirred vigorously and the solution was heated on hot plate to boiling. The solution was filtered using what-man filter paper. The filter paper containing the residue was transferred into 250cm³ beaker and 100cm³ of 0.25M NaOH solution was added into the beaker then 3-5 drops of methyl red indicator was also added and boiled on hot plate. The heat was then put off and 5cm³ of conc. HCl was added until the colour changed to pink. The solution was filtered again using What-man filter paper. The residue in the filter paper was washed five times with 0.2M NH₄Cl solution. The residue was placed in a pre-weighed ceramic crucible and ignited in a furnace at a temperature of 1000°C for 30 minutes. After the ignition the sample and the crucible was allowed to cool at a constant weight in a desiccator (CCNN, 2000).

After the ignition the sample and the crucible was allowed to cool at a constant weight in a desiccator (CCNN, 2000).

The change in weight was used to compute percentage insoluble residue (IR) according to the equation

$$\%IR = \frac{w_2 - w_1}{w} \times 100$$

Where

$\%IR = \text{Percentage insoluble residue}$, $w_2 = \text{final weight of the sample}$, $w_1 = \text{initial weight of the sample}$ and $w = \text{weight of the sample}$

2.5.3 Determination of Loss on Ignition (LOI)

Approximately 3.0 g of the prepared oil cement (POWCC and POWCH5), milled laterites, milled clinker and Bua cement was transferred into a pre-weighed dried ceramic crucible; then each of the crucibles with the sample was ignited at 1000°C in a muffle furnace for 30 minutes. The crucible was then removed, cooled and weighed (C.C.N.N., 2000). The percentage loss on ignition (LOI) was calculated using equation

$$\%LOI = \frac{w_2 - w_1}{w} \times 100$$

Where $\%LOI = \text{Percentage loss on ignition}$ $w_2 = \text{final weight of the sample}$, $w_1 = \text{initial weight of the sample}$ and $w = \text{weight of the sample}$

The Calcinated sample from LOI was ground after it has been cooled in a desiccator using pestle and mortar and 1.3g was weighed and mixed with 9.1g of Lithium Borate (melting agent) in the

ratio of 7:1. The arm of the Claisse machine was pushed back (about 20° backward from the vertical). The fused mixture was poured in a platinum crucible on the Claisse machine.

The arm of the Claisse machine was then pulled until position was about 20° forward from the vertical and security cabinet was closed. The gas, burners and the Claisse machine was turn on. A start on the remote control was pushed and waited for about 8 seconds until a click sound was heard. The flame was lighted using the igniter.

The remote control showed 2 and 0 which marked the end of the program. The gas, burner and the Claisse machine were turn off. The glass bead formed (plate 3.5) was allowed to cooled and picked using suction cup (C.C.N.N., 2000). The procedure was repeated for other samples. The glass bead formed was used for XRF analysis.

2.5.4 X-Ray Fluorescence (XRF) Analysis

The glass bead formed form above was analyzed using Thermoscientific ARL OPTIM'X wavelength dispersive X-ray Fluorescence analyser (WDRF) technique. The XRF is equipped with smartgonio which is a series of multichromators set at -15eV, CaK α and Rhodium anode X-ray tube. The XRF technique reports in oxides of the elements and mineralogical composition of the samples (Boque phases). The analysis was repeated for other samples (C.C.N.N., 2000).

2.6 Blaine Test (Specific Surface Area)

About 3.049g of the sample was pour in a cell containing perforated disc and Blaine filter paper and covered with another filter paper then a plunger was used to press down the sample gently.

The cell with the content was placed in the right arm of the manometer that contains the liquid paraffin. The automatic Blaine machine was then put on and the specific surface area (m²/kg) of the sample was obtained (C.C.N.N., 2000). The procedure was repeated for other samples.

3.0 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Laterite compositions

X-ray fluorecence was used to characterize the two Laterite Samples (Lat A and Lat B). Table 1.0 shows the oxides in weight percent present in the samples. From the Paired t test conducted P value was found to be greater than the α value (that is $P = 0.853 > \alpha = 0.05$) which implies there is no statistical significance difference between between the means of Lat A and Lat B.

All the two laterite samples has high iron content and low LOI values when compare with the literature values obtained by Bandara and Kawamoto (2022) on XRF analysis of two laterites ores-upper (Fe₂O₃ oxide as 26.2 wt%, and LOI as 22.94% and lower (Fe₂O₃ as 31.97wt% and LOI as 13.52%).

In this research Lat B was used because of slightly high iron content and low LOI shown in Table 1.0 (implies low carbonation and Adulteration) as an iron rich correcting material for the production of Class G (MSR) oil well cement.

Table 1.0: Laterite Compositions

Parameter	LatA (wt%)	LatB (wt%)
Fe ₂ O ₃	41.975	42.552
MgO	0.000	0.000
Al ₂ O ₃	0.490	0.336
P ₂ O ₃	0.516	0.620
TiO ₂	0.492	0.454
SO ₃	0.056	0.087
LOI	13.832	11.500
Mc	17.000	18.280
IR	0.6900	0.7130

3.2 Oxides of Cement

There are two types of oxides in both clinker and cement samples namely the major and the minor oxides. The major oxides include CaO, SiO₂, Al₂O₃ and Fe₂O₃ while the minor include MgO, SO₃, oxides of alkali (Na₂O and K₂O) and sometimes the inclusion of other oxides-Cl, TiO₂, P₂O₅, MnO₃ and so forth. The percentages compositions of major and minor oxides and mineralogical compositions as shown in Tables 2.0 and 3.0 respectively are within the specifications of ASTM 150 and API 10a. This means the cements produced were of certain quality.

3.2.1 Major and minor oxides composition

The major oxides include CaO, SiO₂, Al₂O₃ and Fe₂O₃ while the minor include MgO, SO₃, oxides of alkali (Na₂O and K₂O) and sometimes the inclusion of other oxides-Cl, TiO₂, P₂O₅, MnO₃ and so forth.

3.2.1.1 Lime content (CaO)

The CaO content of all the samples is in the range of 63.057-69.9424 wt% (Table 2.0) with POWCC recording the highest value (that is control 0 % laterites) that is POWCC > BUACL > BUAC > POWCH5.

The decrease in CaO content could be due to replacement of some proportions of clinker by laterites whereas high content of CaO recorded for POWCC could be due to gypsum addition.

All the samples recorded high lime contents than the literature value reported by Davoodi et al. (2024) for Class G MSR oil well cement as 59.80 wt% so also BUAC and POWCH5 recorded values of lime content within the range of 58-66 wt% as specified by ASTM 150 while BUACI and POWCC recorded superior values. CaO is the main oxide of any cement compositions, thus its content is usually altered to give cements the desired character (Abdalla *et al.*, 2022).

3.2.1.2 Silica content

The SiO₂ content of all the samples is in the range of 18.7197-21.130 wt% (Table 2.0) with POWCH5 recorded the highest value which could be due heating that is POWCH5>POWCC>BUACL>BUAC. All the samples recorded values of SiO₂ within the range of 18-26 wt% as specified by ASTM C 150. Sample POWCH5 has Silica content close to the literature values reported by Zulkarnain *et al.* (2021) for class G oil well cement and Bayanak *et al.* (2020). as 21.2 and 21.64 wt% respectively. Silica content contributes enormously on the C₃S and C₂S cement phases, and these phases give cement its main characteristics. High silica content is advantageous in oil well cement as the final structure must withstand high temperature and pressure at different zones of the well (Thakkar *et al.* (2020).

3.2.1.3 Aluminum Oxide or Alumina

The Aluminum Oxide or Alumina content of all the samples is in the range 5.1500-5.9796wt% (Table 4.2) with the BUACL recorded the highest value that is BUACL > POWC > POWCH5 > BUAC.

All the samples recorded higher values than the literature values reported by Davoodi *et al.* (2024) as 2.6 wt% for class G MSR and as 3.8 wt % reported by Zulkarnain *et al.* (2021) for class G HSR oil well cement but however, Bahrami *et al.*, 2024 reported a high value of 12.3 wt% compared to all the samples for MSR oil well cement. High alumina content is not desired in OWC, because it enriches the product with alumina phase which is responsible for flash setting (Chen *et al.*, 2024).

3.2.1.4 Iron oxide or Ferrite oxide

The Iron content of all the samples is in the range of 3.5400-5.0313 wt% (Table 2.0) wt% with POWCH5 recording the highest value that is POWCH5 > BUACL > BUAC. The POWCH5 recorded iron content close to the literature value reported by Pang *et al.* (2022). as 5.23 wt% but all the samples has low values compared to the literature value reported by Davoodi *et al.* (2024) as 7.6 wt% for MSR oil well cement.

However sample POWCH5 recorded iron contents superior to the literature value reported by Zulkarnain *et al.* (2021) as 4.76 wt% for class G HSR oil well cement while the remaining samples recorded lower values to all the literatures cited above. However, appreciable improvement was recorded towards achieving high ferrite phase as desired in OWC production at 5% laterites bowc. High Iron content is desirable in OWC, this make the product rich in ferrite phase C₄AF at expense of C₃A which is responsible for flash setting and early setting of cement (Fan *et al.*, (2022). Alumina to ferrite phase ratio (alumina modulus) will be high when iron oxide is low, however low alumina modulus is desired in oil well cement.

The minor oxides in clinker and cement samples include SO₃ and other minor oxides-K₂O, P₂O

3.2.1.5 Sulphur Trioxide (SO₃)

Gypsum used in this research has SO₃ content of 42.11wt% and insoluble residue of 0.11 wt%. Gypsum addition was kept at the optimum level of 4% bowc and this gives the SO₃ content in the range of 0.1815-1.8954wt% (Table 2.0).All the samples recorded value within the maximum acceptable limit of 3.0 wt% of API 10A specifications and below the literature value reported by Zulkarnain *et al.* (2021) for class G oil well as 2.60 wt%.High SO₃ content accelerate hydration reaction of alite phase which is unsuitable for OWC Yang *et al.* (2023).

3.2.1.6 Other minor oxides

Alkali oxide (K₂O): Potassium oxide contents of all the samples are higher than the maximum acceptable limit of 0.75 wt% by API 10A specification (Table 2.0).

Oxides such as Mn₂O₃ and P₂O₅: They are present in minute's quantity.

Table 2.0: Percentage compositions of major and minor oxides of BUACL, POWCC and POWCH5

Parameter	BUACL	POWCC	BUAC	POWCH5
CaO	67.9855	69.9424	64.7400	63.057
SiO ₂	20.099	20.5296	18.7800	21.130
Al ₂ O ₃	5.9796	5.5822	5.1500	5.3470
Fe ₂ O ₃	4.3204	4.1283	3.5400	5.0313
SO ₃	0.1815	1.8954	0.9800	1.6145
K ₂ O	0.1815	1.8954	0.9800	1.6145
P ₂ O ₃	0.6284	0.5769	0.4900	0.5245
Mn ₂ O ₃	0.1321	0.1067	0.1300	0.1366
TiO ₂	0.2752	0.2605	0.2600	0.2676

3.3 Cement Index

3.3.1 Alumina ratio (Alumina Modulus)

Alumina ratio is the ratio of Alumina to the ferrite oxide. The Alumina ratio content of all the samples is in the range of 1.062-1.5200 (Table 3.0) with BUAC recording the highest value that is BUAC> BUACL> POWCC>POWCH5.All the samples recorded values superior to the literature value reported by Zulkarnain *et al.* (2021) as 0.80 when computed from the data obtained for class G HSR oil well cement. However low Alumina ratio of the samples was seen at 5% laterites bowc that is at high percentage of laterites. Low AM values are desirable in OWC, because its sign of high ferrite phase at expense of alumina phase as reported by Yang *et al.* (2023).

3.3.2 Silica ratio (Silica modulus)

Is the ratio of silica to alumina-ferrite oxide. The Silica modulus of all samples is in the range of 1.9515-2.1600 wt% (Table 3.0) with BUAC recording the highest value that is BUAC>POWCC>POWCH5>BUACL. All the samples has lower values compared to the literature values reported by Zulkarnain *et al.* (2021) as 2.4% for class G HSR oil well cement when computed from the data obtained. High SM values (as its sign of high SiO₂) are appreciated in OWC as reported by Thakkar *et al.* (2020).

3.3.3 Lime saturation factor (LSF)

The Lime saturation factor of all samples is in range of 89.9456-104.87 % (Table 3.0) with BUAC recording the highest that is BUAC> BUACL> POWCC> POWCH5. POWCH5 recorded low value to the literature value reported by Zulkarnain *et al.* (2021) as 98.6% while BUAC and POWCC recorded higer values. The decrease in LSF could be due to laterite addition at 5% bowc and heating because high value of LSF.

The LSF controls the ratio of alite to belite in the clinker. A cement with a higher LSF will have a higher proportion of alite to belite than will a cement with a low LSF Nuhu *et al.* (2020) or otherwise (Table 3.0).

3.3.4 Loss on ignition (LOI)

Lost on ignition at high values indicates the amount of carbonation matter and adulteration in cement. All the samples except POWCC and BUAC recorded values of LOI within the maximum acceptable limit of 3.0% as specified by API 10a and ASTM C150 specifications (Table 3.0).

The reason of higher LOI could be due to contamination during milling.

Table 3.0: Cement index of clinker and cement samples

Sample	AM	SM	LSF	LOI
BUACL	1.384	1.9515	102.411	0.760
POWCC	1.352	2.1144	102.619	6.700
BUAC	1.520	2.1600	104.870	5.460
POWCH5	1.062	2.0362	89.9456	2.700

3.4 Mineralogical Compositions

The four mineralogical compositions of cement samples and clinker are Tricalcium silicate (C₃S), Dicalcium silicate (C₂S), Tricalcium aluminate (C₃A) and Tetracalciumalumino ferrite (C₄AF) and the results of their percentage compositions are presented in Table 4.0.

3.4.1 Tricalcium silicate or alite phase (C₃S)

This mineralogical composition is responsible for setting and early strength of the cement paste. The alite contents of samples BUAC, BUACL and POWCC recorded higher values POWCH5 recorded value within the maximum acceptable limit of 48-58 wt % for class G MSR oil well cement as specified by API 10A.

There is decreased in C₃S contents due to replacement of the portion of clinker with laterite which in turn make C₃S contents of POWCH5 to fall within the acceptable range as specified by API 10A(Table 4.0).

3.4.2 Dicalcium silicate or belite phase (C₂S)

The Dicalcium silicate (C₂S) contributes to cement hardening slowly and strength on aging over a month (Pîrvan, 2022).The belite contents of all the samples are lower than the belite content reported in the literature by Zulkarnain *et al.* (2021) as 9.3 wt% except POWCH5 which recorded superior value as 17.2568 wt%.From the results there is increase in C₂S contents in all the samples with laterites addition because of the replacement of portion of the clinker with laterites.

3.4.3 Tricalcium aluminate or celite phase (C₃A)

This the most reactive part of the cement. It liberates large amount of heat during the first few days of hardening and is responsible for flash setting in cement. The celite contents of all the samples are higher than the maximum acceptable limit for class G MSR (≤ 8.0 wt %) except POWCH5 which recorded 5.8245wt% which was in line with the literature value reported by Davoodi *et al.* (2024) for class G MSR as 6.80 wt%.

From the results there is decreased in C₃A contents in all the samples with laterites addition because of the replacement of portion of the clinker with laterites which inturn signifies low alumina ratio and high ferrite phase which is advantageous in the production of oil well cement(Fan *et al.*, 2022).

3.4.4 Tetra-calcium Alumino Ferrite (C₄AF)

It acts as flux i.e. reduces the clinkering temperature (Nguyen and Do, 2022).The sample POWCH5 analysed has C₄AF contents superior to the literature value reported by Zulkarnain *et al.* (2021) as 14.5 wt% for class G HSR oil well cement while BUACL, BUAC and POWCC recorded low values (Table 4.0).

From the results there is an increased in C₄AF contents in all the samples with laterites addition due to the replacement of portion of the clinker with laterites which inturn signifies low alumina ratio and high ferrite which is advantageous in the production of oil well cement as larger setting time are achieved in down hole conditions (Fan *et al.*, 2022), so also resistant to sulphate attack increases (Sotiriadis *et al.*, 2022).

3.4.5 Tetra-calcium Alumino Ferrite plus Twice Tricalcium Aluminate (C₄AF +2C₃A)

The C₄AF+2.C₃A contents of all the samples has values above the maximum acceptable limit of 24 wt% for class G HSR oil well cement as specified by API 10A and below the literature value reported by Bahrami *et al.* (2024.) as 34.9 wt% for MSR oil well cement (Table 4.0). The C₄AF contents contributed more in the sum than C₃A which is a typical of class G HSR based on the specification of API 10A.

Furthermore, Class G MSR and HSR oil well cements are sulphate resistant cements in which for class G HSR the amount of C₃A and (C₄AF+2.C₃A) is restricted to less than or equal to 3 and 24 wt% respectively while for Class G MSR C₃A is restricted to less than or equal to 8 wt% by API 10A specifications, which reduces the formation of sulphate salts and hence lowers the possibility of sulphate attack on the Oil-well cements (Cements, P. 21).

Table 4.0: Mineralogical compositions of clinker and cement samples

Sample	C ₃ S	C ₂ S	C ₃ A	C ₄ AF	C ₄ AF+2C ₃ A
BUACL	78.2601	-4.6192	8.6100	13.2346	30.4546
POWCC	91.4316	-9.8515	8.3773	13.2512	30.0058
BUAC	86.1200	-10.0600	8.1100	11.3916	27.6116
POWCH5	54.4727	17.2568	5.8245	15.7196	27.3686
Class G Portland oil well cement(MRS)*	48-58	-	≤8	-	-

3.5 Blaine Test (Specific Surface Area)

The particle size or fineness of cement in cm²/g or m²/kg in this research was determined using air permeability test with a device called Blaine permeametre. Fineness of cement affects the hydration rate (setting time) and the requirement for the amount of water, retarders and dispersant. Blaine test measures the airflow rate through a bed of powder particles (Cement).

From Figure 1.0 BUAC has the highest specific surface area which could be due to addition of raw limestone during milling followed by POWCH5 while POWCC has the least. However POWCH5 and POWCC have specific surface areas within the range for class G and H oil well cement as specified by API 10A as 270-350 and 220-300m²/kg respectively while BUAC recorded 400m²/kg. The cement with high Blaine value will have high surface area, (Figure 1.0), high kinetic energy of hydration, faster hydration reaction and consequently shorter setting time (Beaudoin and Odler, 2019). However, cement with low Blaine value will be coarser and slower in hydration reaction and longer setting time will be expected because of low kinetic energy of hydration.

Figure 1.0: Time series plot for specific surface area

▪ CONCLUSION

This study successfully developed Class G (MSR) oil-well cement by modifying Type II (BUA) clinker with locally sourced laterite. The laterite, rich in iron oxide (42.552 wt% Fe₂O₃), enhanced the clinker's mineral composition, particularly increasing C₄AF and reducing C₃A thereby improving sulphate resistance and setting time. The final product (POWCH5) met the American Petroleum Institute (API) Specification 10A standards, demonstrating that laterite is a viable and sustainable additive for oil-well cement production.

▪ ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors would like to acknowledge the PTDF Chair at Usmanu Danfodiyo University, Sokoto, Nigeria, for the financial support provided throughout this research, and BUA Cement, Sokoto State, Nigeria, for granting access to their laboratory facilities.

▪ REFERENCES

- Abdalla, A. A., Mohammed, A. S., Rafiq, S., Noaman, R., Qadir, W. S., Ghafor, K., ... and Fairs, R. (2022). Microstructure, chemical compositions, and soft computing models to evaluate the influence of silicon dioxide and calcium oxide on the compressive strength of cement mortar modified with cement kiln dust. *Construction and Building Materials*, 341, 127668. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.conbuildmat.2022.127668>
- Ahmed, A., Mahmoud, A. A., Elkatatny, S. and Gajbhiye, R. (2020). Improving Saudi class G oil-well cement properties using the tire waste material. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acsomega.0c04270>

- API 10A Specifications (2002). American Petroleum Institute's Specification for Materials and Testing for Oil Well Cements, 23rd Edition, Washington DC, American Petroleum Institute
- Bageri, B., Ahmed, A., Al Jaber, J., Elkatatny, S., and Patil, S. (2021). Effect of perlite particles on the properties of oil-well class G cement. *Journal of Petroleum Science and Engineering*, 199, 108344. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.petrol.2021.108344>
- Bahrami, E., Farazmand, R., Norouzi-Apourvari, S., Rashidi, M., Hemmati-Sarapardeh, A., and Ostadhassan, M. (2024). Effect of particle size distribution on the class G oil well cement properties: experimental measurement and intelligent modelling. *Geoenergy Science and Engineering*, 240, 213030. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geoen.2024.213030>
- Bandara, A. B. P., and Kawamoto, K. (2022). LATERITE GRAINS AS A LOW-COST ADSORBENT TO TREAT HEAVY METAL-CONTAMINATED WATER: A REVIEW. *GEOMATE Journal*, 22(94), 73-82. <http://dx.doi.org/10.21660/2022.94.3228>
- Bayanak, M., Zarinabadi, S., Shahbazi, K., and Azimi, A. (2020). Effects of Nano Silica on oil well cement slurry characteristics and control of gas channeling. *South African Journal of Chemical Engineering*, 34, 11-25. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sajce.2020.05.006>
- Beaudoin, J., and Odler, I. (2019). Hydration, Setting and Hardening. *Lea's chemistry of cement and concrete*, 157. https://books.google.com.ng/url?client=ca-google-print&format=googleprint&num=0&id=bpmLDwAAQBAJ&q=http://www.amazon.com/gp/search%3Findex%3Dbooks%26linkCode%3Dqs%26keywords%3D9780081007730&usg=AOvVaw0ZjdR_fshn-MqlQ2bw9aI0&source=gbs_buy_r
- CCNN (2000). Cement Company of Northern Nigeria Laboratory Manual, CCNN Plc, Sokoto, Nigeria, Pp3-22
- Cements, P. 21 The Chemistry of Sulphate-resisting. *Performance of Concrete*, 18.
- Chen, C., Yan, D., Li, X., Liu, M., Cui, C., and Li, L. (2024). Field-tested innovation: Sustainable utilization of secondary alumina dross for flash setting admixtures production. *Journal of Environmental Management*, 358, 120857. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvman.2024.120857>
- Chen, H., Li, N., Unluer, C., Chen, P., and Zhang, Z. (2024). 200 years of Portland cement: Technological advancements and sustainability challenges. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 144500. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2024.144500>
- Davoodi, S., Al-Shargabi, M., Wood, D. A., and Rukavishnikov, V. S. (2024). Recent advances in polymers as additives for wellbore cementing applications: A review. *Fuel*, 357, 129692. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fuel.2023.129692>

- Dissanayake, D. M. S. N., Mantilaka, M. M. M. G. P. G., De Silva, R. T., De Silva, K. M. N., and Pitawala, H. M. T. G. A. (2021). Laterite and its potential as an alternative-bauxite. *Cleaner Materials*, 1, 100016. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.clema.2021.100016>
- Ede, A. N., Olofinnade, O. M., Akpabot, A. I., Oyebisi, S. O., and Nduka, D. O. (2021). Influence of Dicalcium Silicate and Tricalcium Aluminate compounds in different local Cement brands on the compressive strength of normal concrete. *Solid State Phenomena*, 318, 59-69. <https://doi.org/10.4028/www.scientific.net/SSP.318.59>
- Fan, B., Huang, K., Yang, X., Wu, Z., Ni, X., and Cheng, X. (2022). Study on mineral composition design and mechanical properties improvement mechanism of high ferrite oil well cement. *Frontiers in Materials*, 9, 1003776. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmats.2022.1003776>
- Farooq, F., Jin, X., Javed, M. F., Akbar, A., Shah, M. I., Aslam, F., and Alyousef, R. (2021). Geopolymer concrete as sustainable material: A state of the art review. *Construction and Building Materials*, 306, 124762. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.conbuildmat.2021.124762>
- Haha, M. B., Termkhajornkit, P., Ouzia, A., Uppalapati, S., and Huet, B. (2023). Low clinker systems-Towards a rational use of SCMs for optimal performance. *Cement and Concrete Research*, 174, 107312. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cemconres.2023.107312>
- Hasnain Haider, S. A., Emami, E., Masood, K., and Hussain, K. (2024). Manufacturing of cement and petrography of its raw materials. *Journal of Geomine*, 2(2), 50-57. DOI: 10.22077/jgm.2025.7984.1030
- Nguyen, H. T., and Do, Q. M. (2022). Preparation of a novel cement from red mud and limestone. *International Journal of Engineering Research in Africa*, 58, 171-182. <https://doi.org/10.4028/www.scientific.net/JERA.58.171>
- Nuhu, S., Ladan, S., Muhammad, A. U., and Cao, A. F. (2020). Effects and control of chemical composition of clinker for cement production. *International Journal of Control Science and Engineering*, 10(1), 16-21. DOI: 10.5923/j.control.20201001.03
- Pang, X., Sun, L., Chen, M., Xian, M., Cheng, G., Liu, Y., and Qin, J. (2022). Influence of curing temperature on the hydration and strength development of Class G Portland cement. *Cement and Concrete Research*, 156, 106776. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cemconres.2022.106776>
- Paruthi, S., Khan, A. H., Kumar, A., Kumar, F., Hasan, M. A., Magbool, H. M., and Manzar, M. S. (2023). Sustainable cement replacement using waste eggshells: A review on mechanical properties of eggshell concrete and strength prediction using artificial neural network. *Case Studies in Construction Materials*, 18, e02160. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cscm.2023.e02160>
- Pîrvan, A. A. (2022). *Reactive dicalcium silicate binders: Microstructure and transport properties* (Doctoral dissertation, EPFL <https://infoscience.epfl.ch/handle/20.500.14299/5>)

- Sotiriadis, K., Mróz, R., Mácová, P., Mazur, A. S., and Krajnc, A. (2022). Long-term sulfate resistance of synthesized cement systems with variable C3A/C4AF ratio at low temperature or ambient conditions: Insights into the crystalline and amorphous phase assemblage. *Cement and Concrete Research*, 160, 106902. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cemconres.2022.106902>
- Suleimanov, B. A., Veliyev, E. F., and Aliyev, A. A. (2023). *Oil and gas well cementing for engineers*. John Wiley & Sons. books.google.com/Google Scholar
- Thakkar, A., Raval, A., Chandra, S., Shah, M., and Sircar, A. (2020). A comprehensive review of the application of nano-silica in oil well cementing. *Petroleum*, 6(2), 123-129. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.petlm.2019.06.005>
- Thakkar, A., Raval, A., Chandra, S., Shah, M., and Sircar, A. (2020). A comprehensive review of the application of nano-silica in oil well cementing. *Petroleum*, 6(2), 123-129. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.petlm.2019.06.005>
- Vincent, E., Dominic, P., and Kure, M. M. (2020). Assessment of Geotechnical Parameters of Lateritic Soil of Jos and Environs, for Civil Engineering Constructions North Central part of Nigeria. *NIGERIAN ANNALS OF PURE AND APPLIED SCIENCES*, 3(3b), 222-239. <https://doi.org/10.46912/napas.209>
- Yang, Q., Wu, J., Jiang, J., Li, Q., Yu, L., Han, Z., ... and Ye, Z. (2023). Study on the composition and hydration properties at early stages of high-sodium Portland cement clinker under the synergistic effects of SO₃. *Construction and Building Materials*, 400, 132696. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.conbuildmat.2023.132696>
- Zulkarnain, N. N., Farhan, S. A., Sazali, Y. A., Shafiq, N., Abd Rahman, S. H., Abd Hamid, A. I., and Habarudin, M. F. (2021). Reducing the waiting-on-cement time of geopolymer well cement using calcium chloride (CaCl₂) as the accelerator: Analysis of the compressive strength and acoustic impedance for well logging. *Sustainability*, 13(11), 6128. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su13116128>